

Nassarius hafunensis n. sp., a new species of Nassariidae (Gastropoda, Neogastropoda) from Eastern Africa

Nassarius hafunensis n. sp., una nueva especie de Nassariidae (Gastropoda, Neogastropoda) de África Oriental

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ABSTRACT

The new species *Nassarius hafunensis* n. sp. is described based on deep water material from East African Coasts, and its geographical distribution is given. The new species is compared with *Nassarius desmoulioides* (G. B. Sowerby III, 1903), a very similar species from this region.

RESUMEN

Se describe la nueva especie *Nassarius hafunensis* n. sp. en base a material de profundidad procedente de las costas del África Oriental, y se da su distribución geográfica. La nueva especie se compara con *Nassarius desmoulioides* (G. B. Sowerby III, 1903), especie muy similar de esta región.

KEY WORDS: Gastropoda, Nassariidae, *Nassarius*, new species, Indian Ocean, East Africa.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Gastropoda, Nassariidae, *Nassarius*, nueva especie, Océano Índico, África Oriental.

INTRODUCTION

The family Nassariidae is well represented along the coasts of South Africa and the Indian Ocean. In recent decades several expeditions have been conducted in the Mozambique Channel region, the eastern African coast and the islands in the area (see FRAUSSEN *ET AL.*, 2020 for an account of these surveys). The large amount of material obtained has been partially studied in monographic works, but none of them has been exclusively devoted to the analysis

of the family Nassariidae, regarding which information is scattered in multiple papers.

Specimens of the genus *Nassarius* very similar to *Nassarius desmoulioides* (G. B. Sowerby III, 1903) have been obtained from dredges at various depths off the African coast of the Indian Ocean. These specimens, of a remarkably large size, have been found illustrated in a single publication (STEYN & LUSSI, 2005), but confused with *N.*

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desmoulioides. There are a number of aspects that differentiate the specimens in question, in particular their maximum size, which lead to consider them an undescribed species. The purpose of this paper is to describe this new species, to assess its geographical distribution and to compare it with *N. desmoulioides*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied, both that of the new species and that of *N. desmoulioides*, was obtained from reliable shell dealers working in the study area, who obtain them from fishermen. All this material, with the exception of the holotype, is part of the author's per-

sonal collection. Measurements were taken with a digital calliper with an accuracy of 0.1 mm or, in the case of protoconchs, with a micrometric ocular in the stereomicroscope with an accuracy of 0.01 mm. Photographs of whole specimens were taken with a Nikon Coolpix 5700 digital camera. Protoconch images were taken with a Canon 700 D camera and Canon MP-E 65 mm lens and processed by stacking using Cognisys Stackshot and Helicon Focus 8 application. All the images were post-processed with Photoshop.

Abbreviations:

CG: Carles Gili collection. Barcelona, Spain.

MZB: Museu de Ciències Naturals de Barcelona collection, Barcelona, Spain.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Superfamily BUCCINOIDEA Rafinesque, 1815

Family NASSARIIDAE Iredale, 1916

Subfamily NASSARIINAE Iredale, 1916

Genus *Nassarius* Duméril, 1805

Type species (by subsequent monotypy, Froriep, 1806): *Buccinum arcularia* Linnaeus, 1758. Recent.

Nassarius hafunensis n. sp. (Fig. 1A, Fig. 2A-I, Fig. 3A-C)

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Nassarius desmoulioides – Steyn & Lussi, 2005: 132, text-fig. (misidentification)

Type material. *Holotype*: Mozambique • 1 shell (H=28.1 mm, D=16.8 mm; Fig. 2 A-C); off Zavora; 120-450 m.; C. Afonso leg.; MZB 2023-0998. *Paratypes*: Mozambique • 7 shells + 1 juv.; Sep. 2001, Nov. 2001, Aug. 2018; C. Afonso, C. A. Verdasca leg.; CG 1496-N.

Other material studied: South Africa • 1 shell; off Natal coast; 400-500 m; A. D. Seccombe leg.; CG 2677-N • 2 shells; Agulhas Bank; 200 m.; Dick Carter leg.; CG 2412-N. Mozambique • 2 shells, off South Mozambique; 150-250 m; CG 1605-N. Somalia • 3 shells; Ras Hafun; 150-250 m; 1988, 1993; L. Bozzetti, J. Saltó leg.; CG 918-N.

Material of *N. desmoulioides* studied for comparison: South Africa • 2 shells; off KwaZulu-Natal; CG 434-N • 6 shells; off Durban, Natal; 150 m; CG 554-N • 10 shells; Algoa Bay; 100-150 m; CG 578-N • 3 shells; Richard's Bay, KwaZulu-Natal; CG 1087-N • 1 shell; Cape St. Francis; 150 m; CG 2383-N • 1 shell; Port Edwards, KwaZulu-Natal; 90-100 m; CG 2755-N. Mozambique • 3 shells; no further locality details; 100-180 m; CG 1611-N • 4 shells; Sofala; 120-170 m; CG 773-N • 4 shells; Zavora; 124-140 m; CG 1364-N • 2 shells; Beira; 135-150 m; CG 1365-N • 1 shell; Nacala Bay; CG 2767-N.

Type locality: Mozambique, Inhambane province, off Zavora, 120 to 450 m.

Etymology: The name *hafunensis* of the species refers to Ras Hafun, Somalia, located at the easternmost point of Africa, from which the first specimens were obtained.

Figure 1. Comparison between *Nassarius* spp. A: *Nassarius hafunensis* n. sp., Somalia, Ras Hafun, height 29.6 mm, CG 918-N; B: *Nassarius desmoulioides* (G. B. Sowerby III, 1903), Mozambique, Sofala, height 18.9 mm, CG 773-N. Both specimens are represented at the same scale.

Figura 1. Comparación entre Nassarius spp. A: Nassarius hafunensis n. sp., Somalia, Ras Hafun, altura 29.6 mm, CG 918-N; B: Nassarius desmoulioides (G. B. Sowerby III, 1903), Mozambique, Sofala, altura 18.9 mm, CG 773-N. Ambos especímenes están representados a la misma escala.

Description of the holotype: Protoconch multispiral of 3.25 convex smooth whorls (including nucleus), exposed part 0.96 mm high and 0.88 mm diameter, with a very small nucleus, first 1.5 whorls ochre, the rest yellowish. The transition to the teleoconch presents 5 low opisthocyrt crests (Fig. 3).

Teleoconch of 7 whorls, 28.1 mm high and 16.8 maximum diameter, with a tall stepped spire of very convex whorls (65% of height), ornamented with ribs and spiral cords, last whorl globose almost as tall as wide. Ribs narrow, orthocline, initially narrower than their interspaces, becoming slightly prosocline towards the aperture, thinner and more closely set together, decreasing to disappear in the last quarter of the body whorl. Fifty-five ribs on the penultimate whorl and 51 on the last whorl, and five ribs are present next to the outer lip. Spiral cords narrow, rounded, separated by narrow grooves widening on the later part of the shell, reaching the edge of the outer lip, forming small granules at their intersections with the ribs. Twelve cords

on penultimate whorls and 19 on the last whorl, the three basal more prominent. Aperture subcircular, not very large. Convex outer lip with a wavy profile, thickened externally and with 16 narrow and rather deep internal denticles, of which the abapical and the two adapical are thicker. Columella strongly concave in its middle part, with a prominent parietal denticle, a wide anal canal, and with a marked abapical fold and three slight folds above it. Columellar callosity thin and not very spread out on the preceding whorl, laminar and raised in the siphonal canal region. Siphonal canal short, twisted, and separated from the base of the body whorl by a deep and wide groove, ornamented with 5 external spiral cords.

Colour of background whitish yellowish with four poorly marked brownish axial bands in the last quarter of body whorl, and some little brown spots along the spire and the last whorl; outer lip, callosity and interior white.

Species variability: The number of teleoconch whorls varies between 6 and

7.75, 7 being the most common. The dimensions vary from 21.4 mm to 35.3 mm in height, with an average of 26.7 mm. The number of ribs is highly variable because these are blurring in some specimens, especially on a more or less extensive part of the last whorl. There are between 22 and 57 ribs on the penultimate whorl and between 26 and 51 on the last whorl. In Somalian specimens the ribs are more constant on the shell, and the number of cords is also less variable, between 8 and 12 on the penultimate whorl and between 15 and 25 on the last whorl, the latter number quite

linked to the height of the whole shell. The external thickening of the lip can form, or not at all, a well-defined varix and the internal labial denticles vary between 14 and 18. The quantity and extension of brown bands and spots are variable, some of the Somalian specimens have a yellowish-brown tonality not present in the rest. Not all specimens have the protoconch stained brown, in many specimens it is completely white or yellowish.

Distribution: The species is known only off eastern Africa, from South Africa to Somalia.

DISCUSSION

Nassarius hafunensis is a deep-sea species; the available data place it between 120 and 500 m in muddy-sandy bottoms. The only image found in the literature corresponding to the new species is that of STEYN & LUSSI (2005: 132), misidentified as *N. desmoulioides*, regarding which they point out that "trawled specimens (200-350 m) can reach a size of 32 mm". In fact, the most evident difference between these two species lies with its dimensions. SOWERBY III (1903: 219), in the original description of *N. desmoulioides*, gave 21 mm as height, the height found in the literature is 20-23 mm (BARNARD, 1959; KENSLEY, 1973; CERNOHORSKY, 1984; ROBIN, 2008; MARAIS & SECCOMBE, 2010), and the comparison material averages 17.8 mm. The average of the specimens of *N. hafunensis* is 26.7 mm and the maximum height measured for this species is 35.3 mm, while for the largest *N. desmoulioides* is 22.3 mm in the comparison material.

On the other hand, *N. hafunensis* reaches up to 7.75 teleoconch whorls, with an average of 6.5, while for *N. desmoulioides*, the original description indicated 8 whorls from which the protoconch must be excluded (at least 3 whorls as can be seen in KAICHER, 1983, card 3463) and, in the comparison material, no more than 6.5 whorls, and

usually 6, are counted. For an equal number of whorls, *N. hafunensis* is much larger than *N. desmoulioides* (Fig.1). Therefore, the length does not depend on the number of whorls, but corresponds to a different growth pattern of the shell. The last whorl of *N. desmoulioides* is not so inflated as it usual is in *N. hafunensis*. The kind of ornamentation is very similar in both species. However, axial ribs in *N. hafunensis* are narrower and less prominent, especially in the two last whorls, and are much more numerous than in *N. desmoulioides*. The number of spiral cords, in contrast, is more similar in both species. The granulations of the two subsutural cords in *N. desmoulioides* are always more pronounced and tend to be slightly pointed, whereas this is not the case in *N. hafunensis*. The colouring is also different, the large profusion and width of ochre-brown spots in *N. desmoulioides* is never found in *N. hafunensis*, species with white-ivory colour much more homogeneous, and its protoconch does not regularly presents the apex reddish-brown as *N. desmoulioides*.

Despite having the same overall morphology, differences have been observed in the protoconch dimensions, those of *N. hafunensis* being slightly larger in number of whorls, in height and diameter than those of *N. desmoulioides*. However, the number of

Figure 2. *Nassarius hafunensis* n. sp. A-C: holotype, Mozambique, off Zavora, 28.1 mm, MZB 20230998 (ex CG 1496-N), 120-450 m. D-F: Somalia, Ras Hafun, 27.4 mm, CG 918-N, 150-250 m. G-I: South Africa, Agulhas Bank, 23.4 mm, CG 2412-N, 200 m.

Figura 2. *Nassarius hafunensis* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, Mozambique, frente a Zavora, 28,1 mm, MZB 20230998 (ex CG 1496-N), 120-450 m. D-F: Somália, Ras Hafun, 27,4 mm, CG 918-N, 150-250 m. G-I: África do Sul, Banco Agulhas, 23,4 mm, CG 2412-N, 200 m.

Figure 3. *Nassarius hafunensis* n. sp. Protoconch of the holotype. A: sagittal view; B: oblique view; C: lateral view.

Figure 3. *Nassarius hafunensis* n. sp. Protoconcha del holotipo. A: vista sagital; B: vista oblicua; C: vista lateral.

measurements that have been carried out are not sufficient to support a significant difference.

The depth where *N. desmoulioides* lives, between 40 m. and those 182.88 m. (100 fathoms) in the original description, are not as deep as these of *N. hafunensis*, but the distributions are overlapping. Kilburn & Seccombe (in MARAIS & SECCOMBE, 2010) gave a depth range between 40 and 350 m for *N. desmoulioides* and, probably, the latter value corresponds to a confusion with *N. hafunensis*. Geographical distribution differs between both species; *N. desmoulioides* does not seem to live north of Mozambique. *N. hafunensis*, from the known material, reaches Somalia, almost into the Gulf of Aden.

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Nassarius desmoulioides was also confused by some authors (KNUDSEN, 1956 [misspelled *Nassa desmouleoides*]; ADAM & KNUDSEN, 1984; ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI, 2004) with a species from West Africa, later described as *Nassarius arcadioi* by ROLÁN & HERNÁNDEZ (2005).

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